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FACING THE FEAR: UNRAVELING GLOSSOPHOBIA GRIP ON LANGUAGE LEARNING SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explored how students at Abuyog Community College overcome their fear of public speaking and develop emotional resilience in an academic setting. Using multiple case analysis, the study focused on four purposively selected English students, chosen based on their self-reported challenges with speaking before an audience and willingness to participate in in-depth interviews. The research was guided by Cognitive Behavioral Theory and Social Learning Theory to understand their experiences and coping strategies.

The study revealed four major themes: overcoming fear, self-discovery, positive relationships, and personal development. It concluded that emotional growth depends not only on internal reflection but also on environments with affirming and supportive relationships. Students flourish personally and academically when they can express themselves without fear. Feedback from participants highlighted that, through mental preparation, practice, and support, they overcame anxiety and gained confidence. The research underscores the importance of creating safe, positive spaces that promote authenticity, emotional regulation, and holistic student growth.

This paper resolved a serious gap in the literature: the scarcity of studies that discuss the effects of glossophobia on BSED English students and which pedagogical or language learning processes could be effectively used to reduce the influence of glossophobia. Finally this research, with its unstudied intersection, provides a significant contribution to the research and practice of the field of education, as well as applied linguistics, and to curriculum design, teacher training, and student support system.

keywords: *glossophobia, cognitive, social learning, anxiety, emotional strength*

INTRODUCTION

Glossophobia, or the fear of public speaking, affects millions of people all over the world. It is a widespread phobia, which is followed by death, spiders, and heights (Mental Health.com, 2024). Medical News Today (2023) states that it is present in 15-30 percent of the global population, and approximately 10 percent of individuals with glossophobia claim that it disrupts their lives, including their employment and education. This can bring about much fear in language learning especially in the second language like English. Glossophobia is quite a significant impediment to college studies and career growth. Most students that have a high level of public speaking anxiety react by declining to participate in oral projects or classroom discussions even though these activities are learning tasks that are required (Conception et al., 2023). Tamayo and Caber (2022) note that the many factors that drive this fear, among others, are communication apprehension, test anxiety, and negative feedback fear.

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Moreover, a relative research gap is still apparent in examining how this fear is particularly manifested among second year BSED English students in Abuyog Community College. With the aim of developing a detailed picture of the way the glossophobia is reflected in students' language learning, this paper sought to explore on how it influences their confidence and participation in language learning and performance.

The fear of speaking in front of people, known as glossophobia has been a major obstacle to learning a language successfully. Research has revealed that glossophobic students may have problems with oral communication, consequently reducing their participation, confidence and they will not learn easily. The researchers are experiencing it even themselves. The concept of glossophobia may turn into a barrier to the idea of communication between English college students, who may fail to discuss, present their ideas, and enhance their verbal communication skills which are the key aspects of mastering the language. Certain researchers point out that highly anxious students are likely to do poorly in grammar tests relative to the lowly anxious students.

If glossophobia is not addressed, it may impede academic and career development, reduce self-confidence, reduce opportunities, cause social isolation, and produce stress. The statement mentioned above led us to research on the impact of glossophobia on the language learning process through the analysis of the real cases, to discover the patterns of conduct of students, their strategies to deal with the situation, and the efficiency of the learning process under those conditions. The main step to achieving a good communication and confidence is overcoming it.

Statement of the Problem

This study explores the experience of BSED English Major students on glossophobia (fear of public speaking) and examine how this affect their language learning mechanism.

Specifically, the research aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How do the participants display glossophobia?
2. What are the manifestations of person experiencing glossophobia?
3. How does glossophobia influence their language learning mechanism?
4. How does the participants overcome the predicament and what coping mechanism they employed?
5. How do the researchers critically reflect on their study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The research used multiple case study research design, which is presented by Creswell, (2007), to examine the issues of 2nd year BSED English students who reported the effects of glossophobia. Multiple case study was the most suitable design to inquire and compare experiences of various distinct groups so that they can be studied thoroughly in their anxiety of public speaking in diverse contexts. Through the analysis of several cases, the study sought to determine what is common among the respondents and what was specific to them, which was aligned with Yin (2014), who pointed out that multiple cases studies are significant in creating an all-inclusive understanding.

Research Participants. Using purposive sampling, 5 education students who experience glossophobia. All the participants were involved in the active process of language learning, i.e., oral presentations and interactive discussions, in which the anxiety of speaking before an audience can greatly affect their performance. Their distinct insights played a vital role in studying the connection between glossophobia and learning a language and in determining factors that would affect their academic performance and involvement

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Research Instrument. The research employed naturalistic observation and semi-structured interview to collect data. According to Yin (2014), semi-structured interviews were flexible in discussing the experiences of college English students in detail and those who experienced glossophobia. Naturalistic observation was the observation of the participants in their natural setting without making them aware of the observer to record their behavior under natural conditions. Bertak (1971) accentuated its usefulness in the interpretation of real-world behaviors. These approaches when combined gave contextual information that was important in understanding the experiences of the students. A reflexive journal was employed in observation and interviews to capture the thoughts, feelings, and observations of the researcher. It fostered self-realization, bias minimization, and subjectivity of the researcher, which increased the credibility and transparency of the study in terms of ethics.

Validation of Research Instrument. The researchers consulted the experts to enhance the methodological rigor of the study and to have a sound approach in data collection and analysis. Additionally, the case study was thoroughly validated with triangulation, expert review, and feedback of participants. The multi-faceted methodology increased precision and authenticity of the results, which enabled exploration of the topic at a deeper level. Triangulation was conducted through the gathering of data on three important sources: naturalistic observation, semi-structured interviews, and participant feedback. The researcher contrasted these sets of data to discover some common themes and confirm results. To make sure that results were consistent and rich, the observational notes were aligned with interview answers and participant reflections. This was to ensure the dependability of the results and to have a broader view of what the students had to go through with glossophobia.

Locale of the Study. The study was conducted at Abuyog Community College where researchers are enrolled. The researchers selected this institution based on providing a relevant setting of observing and interviewing college students who experienced glossophobia and its impact on the language learning mechanism.

Ethical Considerations. This study strictly adhered to ethical guidelines to make sure that all participants are safeguarded and dignified. All participants gave informed consent prior to any collection of data. They were provided with a clear explanation of the study's purpose, procedures and their rights including right to withdraw any time without any consequences. Confidentiality of personal information and responses was also assured to the participants and the information will be used purely on academic basis. To preserve the anonymity, no reports and publications revealed participant identities and all the data obtained was properly stored. The study adhered to the principles of transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in the processing of personal data, which are stated in Republic Act No. 10173 also referred to as the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Data Gathering Procedure. The study began with getting informed consent of participants to make sure that ethical considerations were adhered to. In order to discuss the individual experience of the participants concerning glossophobia, semi-structured interviews were made, and each participant had a different case that can be compared with others. To have the right data, the audio recording was recorded with the consent of the participants interview guide to be specific and relevant. A formal letter was also written to the college president seeking permission to carry out the research in the institution stating the objective of the research, the methodology and ethical aspects of the research. To maintain the integrity and reliability of the study, confidentiality and anonymity were observed over the process.

Data Analysis. The cross-case analysis facilitated a comparative study of qualitative data, identifying trends and differences in personal experiences of glossophobia. Thematic coding and coding reliability ensured consistent theme identification, while reflexive approaches enabled deeper interpretation of participants. Triangulation, expert checking, and participant feedback enhanced the credibility and richness of the findings, providing in-depth insights and robust theoretical and practical outcomes

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stories in this paper reveal realistic views of the real experiences of the individuals in question, bringing out themes and sub-themes.

1. Overcoming Public Speaking Fears

The student's physical symptoms, nervousness, sweating, trembling reflect their anxiety inside. Cognitive Behavioral Theory suggests these reactions can be managed through practice and relaxation. These symptoms are evident in Participant 1's description: *"Of course, very first kay I am feeling nervous. And then signs ko siton are trembling especially sa kamot, and then mamalhas, and then fast heartbeat"* ("Of course, at first, I feel nervous. Then the signs I notice are trembling, especially in my hands, sweating, and a fast heartbeat"). This is in line with the results of Manalang (2025) qualitative research on the Grade 9 students, which indicated similar physical manifestations of anxiousness in front of the group such as trembling, sweating, and increased heart rate.

1.1 Managing Nervousness and Anxiety. Cognitive Behavioral Theory (CBT) suggests that anxiety often stems from negative thought patterns, and by identifying and re-framing these thoughts, individuals can reduce their emotional distress. Participant 1's insight— *"In order for you to bring yourself back, you need to relax your mind because it is a cognitive part. So, you have to deal with it cognitively as well."* This reflects a clear understanding of how anxiety operates and how it can be managed through intentional mental strategies.

1.2 Building Confidence Through Practice and Preparation. Repeated practice—like speaking, performing, or taking exams—reduces uncertainty and builds confidence. Preparation helps anticipate challenges, easing anxiety and strengthening self-belief (Rahimulla et al., 2025). As Participant 4 shared, *"Pag try kona, nasiring ko na kaya koman ngay-an, need la talaga sin practice para ma cope up an akon fears. Ada la talaga it fears, need mo la marealize na kaya mo"* ("**When I tried it, I told myself I could do it. I just really needed practice to cope with my fears. The fear is always there, you just need to realize that you can overcome it**"). This insight reflects how repeated exposure to challenging tasks helps reduce anxiety and builds a sense of competence. In an article of Rahimulla et al. (2025) results had found out that practice, preparation, and supportive conditions played a great role in assisting students to overcome anxiety when addressing an audience, as well as to develop confidence.

2. Self-Discovery and Authenticity. Self-discovery is the ongoing journey of exploring the thoughts, emotions, values, desires, and beliefs. It involves peeling back the layers shaped by society, family, and past experiences to uncover your authentic self. (Wilson, T. D., & Dunn, E. W., 2004). Participant 3 shared "During the first year that was evident, siguro that was the very peak of my glossophobia. I was appointed as the group leader, but I don't have the interest, I feared to messed up." Initially, the student struggled with glossophobia fear of public speaking and felt disconnected from the leadership role assigned to them. Similarly Participant 2 shared almost the same experience. "You

have to start with people you're comfortable with, and then slowly branch out from there. But you should still be the same—you have to stay authentic”.

This observation is based on the Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) which states that people acquire behaviors and emotional reactions through observation and social interaction in the environment.

2.1 Embracing One's True Self and Letting Go of Pretenses. Embracing one's true self means shedding the masks we wear to fit in or impress others, and instead choosing honesty over performance (Cohen, I. S., 2023). Participant 4 explained “...mayda kola gihap thoughts nga what if magfail la gihapon ako sa pag speak, but mayda liwat saakon other side, bagan okay la mag fails basta gin-try.” (“*I still had thoughts like, what if I fail again at speaking? But there was also another side of me that felt—it's okay to fail as long as I tried.*”) This reflects a moment of inner honesty and vulnerability. Instead of pretending to be confident or hiding behind a facade, the student acknowledges their fear while also embracing the courage to try anyway.

2.2 Finding Comfort in Being Authentic and Genuine.

When students let go of pretenses and allow their genuine selves to shine through, they not only build deeper connections with those around them but also cultivate inner peace (Nachfigall, V., & Wirth, J., 2024). Participant 2 said “Because of the fear, I've created this version of myself that is so different of who I am just to fit in.

According to Pope (2024), *the way to authenticity is not always a straightforward one; it is influenced by the experiences of the past and safety decisions. It helps to sustain the notion that it is best to be who one is.*

3. The Power of Supportive Relationship

According to Bandura (1977), individuals learn behaviors, attitudes, and emotional responses by observing and interacting with others in their social environment. This is true in the statement of one participant who said “ Malaking tulong ang encouragement ng mga guro at kaklase ko kasi kapag sinasabihan nila akong kaya ko, kahit paano ay lumalakas ang loob ko” (“**The encouragement from my teachers and classmates really helps because when they tell me that I can do it, it somehow gives me the courage.**”) It reflects how **positive social interactions**—particularly verbal encouragement can influence a learner's emotional state and behavior.

3.1 Surrounding Oneself with Positive and Encouraging People. When learners are surrounded by positive and encouraging people such as empathetic peers, mentors, or educators they are more likely to model adaptive coping strategies, internalize constructive attitudes, and feel a sense of belonging that reduces anxiety. This coincide with the statement of Participant 4 “Dire ko ginma-mind a shaking, always ko ginkikita an tawo na nagmo-motivate saakon” (“**I don't mind the shaking; I always focus on the person who motivates me.**)

3.2 The Impact of Supportive Relationships on Personal Growth and Confidence. Beck (1964) emphasized that modifying distorted cognition can lead to improved emotional regulation and behavioral outcomes. As participant 3 mentioned “*it happened when I had a great instructor where they've seen this potential!*” It highlights how **being seen and supported by someone in a position of guidance**, can be a powerful catalyst for personal development and self-belief.

4. Personal Growth and Development. One of the most powerful aspects of this process is **learning from mistakes and embracing imperfections**

4.1 Learning from Mistakes and Embracing Imperfections. When individuals allow themselves to reflect on what went wrong without harsh self-judgment, they begin to understand their patterns, triggers, and areas for growth (Taju Coaching Team, 2024). Participant 3 stated "...that thoughts make me think of maybe this is my limit. But again, that is because of glossophobia. I structure my thought of the supporting details and how am I going to end." **Personal Growth and Development** involves taking risks, learning from setbacks, and recognizing one's own potential through experience.

4.2 Cultivating Self-awareness and Self-improvement. Through self-awareness, individuals can identify limiting beliefs, challenge negative thought patterns, and set meaningful goals. Participant 1 said "You will not mind your surroundings. Another is you will encourage yourself. Like iton simple la nga 'kaya mo iton, nag practice ka balitaw.'" ("**You won't pay attention to your surroundings. Another thing is you'll encourage yourself—like simply saying, 'You can do it, you practiced after all.'**") Public speaking or performing, they try to block out distractions around them and focus inward. Instead of letting anxiety take over, they **mentally motivate themselves** by reminding themselves of their preparation and capability.

Research Reflexivity

Reflexivity is the process of engaging in self-reflection about who we are as researchers, how our subjectivity and biases guide and inform the research process, and how our worldview is shaped by the research we do and vice versa (Wilkinson, 1988). The researchers realized that as they developed anxiety about public speaking, they were more likely to interpret the stories of participants based on their own experiences on public speaking anxiety. Participants' strategies of coping, and their paths to authenticity were close to their own, that made them think about the emotional and cultural forces, that affect communication. They established trust with the participants due to their empathy and knowledge about the subject matter, but they also had to be careful not to project our assumptions on the experiences of participants. This self-reflective process assisted them in being ethically sensitive and being open to different views.

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the significant impact of public speaking anxiety on students' confidence, social engagement, and emotional well-being. The findings suggest that targeted interventions rooted in Cognitive Behavioral Theory (CBT)—such as structured practice, cognitive reframing, and relaxation techniques—can effectively support students in overcoming glossophobia. Participant narratives reveal that consistent exposure to speaking opportunities, coupled with emotional support and self-awareness, fosters resilience and personal growth.

Overall, this research underscores the need for holistic approaches to student development, where psychological safety, skill-building, and emotional regulation are prioritized alongside academic performance. These insights can inform future programs, policies, and pedagogical strategies aimed at nurturing confident, communicative, and emotionally resilient learners.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To support students with glossophobia, teachers should integrate CBT-based techniques such as reframing negative beliefs, deep breathing, and mental rehearsal into their teaching. Low-pressure speaking exercises paired with positive feedback can reduce anxiety and build confidence. Schools must promote inclusive, non-discriminatory environments that encourage self-expression, along with mentoring in emotional intelligence and role modeling.

Educators and school counselors may consider integrating public speaking exercises into the curriculum, not only to enhance communication skills but also to build emotional competence.

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Creating safe, supportive environments where students can practice and receive constructive feedback may reduce fear and promote self-efficacy. Furthermore, recognizing the role of social support—such as encouragement from teachers and peers—can help students feel seen, valued, and motivated to persist despite discomfort.

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